

SIGNS AND EARLY SYMPTOMS OF PREGNANCY. METHODS FOR DETERMINING PREGNANCY

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Annotation. Signs of pregnancy, its first symptoms, every woman wants to know these symptoms and feel them as soon as possible. Pregnancy is a wonderful and special time. Usually, vomiting and nausea associated with pregnancy begin at 5-6 weeks of pregnancy, and a delay in menstruation is the first sign that pregnancy may have begun. Pregnancy can feel unusual events occurring in the body even earlier.

Keywords: fetus, pelvic area, abdomen, body, symptoms, hormone, mammary gland, bladder, face, menstrual cycle, ovulation.

Primary signs and symptoms of pregnancy - the earlier a woman detects pregnancy, the more time she has to undergo qualified specialized medical examinations. After fertilization of the egg, a number of hormonal changes occur in the woman's body. If you notice the following signs, you can take a home pregnancy test to confirm pregnancy. Missed menstruation. All women know about this symptom. After fertilization of the egg, the menstrual cycle is lengthened, which is why the endometrium of the uterus is now used to form the placenta of the fetus. However, it should not be forgotten that in some diseases the menstrual cycle is also lengthened. Nausea. The appearance of these symptoms often begins with the 1.5th month of the fetus's cycle, and in some women it can be observed even after fertilization. Nausea can also be caused by diseases of the gastrointestinal tract. Weakness and drowsiness. This symptom occurs due to the accelerated metabolism in the body, which makes the body tired and the hormone progesterone causes drowsiness. In addition, a metallic taste in the mouth is also one of the first signs of pregnancy. As a result of hormones changing the taste characteristics of the female body, she may like tastes that she did not like before. In the early days of pregnancy, enlarged nipples become painful. Enlarged and painful mammary glands. This indicates that the mammary glands are very sensitive to hormonal changes. If you go to the toilet many times in the evening even if the bladder is not full, this is a sign that the HCG (chorionic gonadotropin hormone) has begun to be produced in large quantities during pregnancy. In addition, the color of urine may also

change during pregnancy. Secondary signs of pregnancy are back pain and radiating pain in the lower back. However, such pain can also be observed in kidney diseases. Feeling of heaviness in the pelvic area - blood circulation in this area increases and the woman begins to feel heaviness and pressure. Irritability and mood swings - many women have frequent mood swings and irritability, which can lead to insomnia - insomnia can be observed as a result of which they feel tired. Headaches can be observed due to hormonal changes affecting the nervous system. Increased appetite, increased sense of smell and taste - if a woman did not pay attention to certain smells before, her sensitivity to smells increases during pregnancy. Body weight changes - body weight increases in order for the woman's body to provide the fetus with nutrition. Implantation bleeding - the discharge of blood-mixed fluid from the woman's vagina when the fertilized egg attaches to the uterine lining is one of the secondary symptoms of pregnancy. Flatulence - flatulence is observed in the intestines as a result of the softening effect of hormones on the intestines. Increased venous blood vessels in the breast area - after the onset of pregnancy, the body also prepares for feeding it. The color of the nipples also darkens. Weakened immunity - due to the weakening of the immune system during pregnancy, a woman's body becomes more susceptible to common colds and ARVI. Redness of the skin of the face - as a result of the effect of hormones on the capillaries, blood vessels dilate. Various rashes on the face - even if a woman has never had any problems with her skin before, acne appears on the face during pregnancy. This is explained by hormonal imbalance. Swelling of the face, arms and legs - during pregnancy, the body tries to retain more fluid. For this reason, swelling of varying degrees is observed on the face, arms and legs.

Signs of pregnancy include an increase in basal temperature; As a result of increased production of the hormone progesterone, body temperature can rise to 37 degrees; Pigmentation disorders on the white line of the abdomen - a characteristic symptom for pregnant women, a "strip" appears from the navel to the pubic symphysis. The probability of getting pregnant after ovulation is very low. After ovulation, the egg can be fertilized within 12-24 hours. But after that, the egg is considered unsuitable for fertilization. Therefore, women who want to get pregnant should definitely know the day of ovulation and monitor their menstrual cycle. Couples planning a pregnancy are recommended to have sex on the fertile days before ovulation and on the day of ovulation. It can be difficult to plan a pregnancy if you do not control your menstrual cycle and do not know exactly the day of ovulation. Methods of determining pregnancy - Modern,

specialized diagnostic methods allow you to determine pregnancy from the fifth day of pregnancy. It is almost impossible to determine the first three days of pregnancy. Many women planning to have a baby usually use home pregnancy tests to determine pregnancy as soon as they notice the first signs of pregnancy. Because these tests are both convenient to use and reliable. If you follow the rules for conducting the test, you can definitely get an accurate and accurate result. How many days does a pregnancy test determine the pregnancy? According to data, women with a regular menstrual cycle can take a pregnancy test from the first days of the next menstruation. And the average gestation period is about four weeks. Ultrasound examinations are safe for both mother and fetus. Ultrasound examination (UTT) can detect pregnancy from the 3rd week of pregnancy. The examination is performed using abdominal or transvaginal sensors. In addition to UTT, it is also possible to determine the signs of pregnancy on the 20th day of the menstrual cycle using express methods. Sometimes women use some methods that are not scientifically proven, even when the most convenient way to determine pregnancy at home is a pregnancy test. For example, using substances such as iodine and salt. Determining pregnancy with iodine - you put your urine in a clean container. Then you add 2 drops of iodine to it. If the iodine dissolves immediately, pregnancy is not present, if the iodine does not dissolve for a few seconds and does not spread, pregnancy is considered to have occurred. Determining pregnancy with salt - to determine pregnancy at home using table salt, equal amounts of salt and urine are taken and mixed. For example, 1 tablespoon of salt is added to 1 tablespoon of urine. After leaving the mixture for a few minutes, if the salt dissolves, the result is negative. If it accumulates, the woman is considered pregnant. This method is also not based on any scientific evidence. These methods performed at home may accidentally give the same result as a pregnancy test. You should not forget that both methods give the same results, and that the methods performed at home with salt and iodine are correct and reliable. Therefore, if you start to notice pregnancy symptoms, it is advisable to take a reliable pregnancy test within the recommended period.

Conclusion

Pregnancy can often be determined by signs and symptoms. The most common symptoms are: missed period, nausea, frequent urination. However, some women may not have these symptoms. The most reliable ways to determine: Home tests, Blood tests, Ultrasound. If there is a positive result, it is necessary to undergo a doctor's examination, which will be beneficial for both

the mother and the child. Of course, you should follow the doctor's advice, it is necessary to undergo examinations every month, so that a healthy mother and a healthy child are born.

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